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Prevalence of Ectoparasites and Endoparasites in Tilapia (*Oreochromis Niloticus*) from Ureje River in Ado Ekiti

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ABSTRACT

This study provides the first investigation on parasites of *O. niloticus* in Ureje River. A total of sixty samples of *O. niloticus* were purchased from a fish farm around Ureje River over a period of six (6) months and subjected to parasitological examinations. 33 (55%) of the total sample were infected with parasites. In all, nine genera of Protozoa, three species of Nematode and one species of Trematode were isolated from different organs of *O. niloticus*. The height and weight of *O. niloticus* were subjected to regression analysis, which revealed a significant relationship between height and weight as r value (0.942, $H_0 P=0$; $H_1 P\neq 0$) is approximating 1. The prevalence of parasites on *O. niloticus* ranged from 10% to 100%, with mean prevalence of 45%, mean intensity of 177% and mean abundance of 55%. The mean infection was highest in October (300) and lowest in August (80), the prevalence of protozoa isolated from *O. niloticus* varied from 1.67% (*Chilodonella* and *Coccidia* sp) to an optimal prevalence value of 16.7% in *Piscinoodinium* sp. while *Allocreadium lobatum* has a prevalence value of 8.3%. Infection could be influenced by high/low rain influx during the rainy/dry season as fishes are susceptible to heavy infestation with parasites during the early rain. However, differences in the abundance and prevalence of these parasites may be dependent on host-pathogen relationship, whether or not the immune system compromised.

Keywords

Parasites, *O. niloticus*, Protozoa, Nematode, Ureje River

Introduction

Tilapias, originated from Africa, have been introduced to different parts of the world. They are important sources of protein that are sold commercially in different part of Nigeria and other African countries. They are vital aquaculture and invasive fishes in the world and have been introduced to over 140 countries around the world¹. They are resilient species and can grow in extreme conditions². Tilapias are important source of

human diet because they contain proteins, lipids and micronutrients which help in various ways to keep human healthy³. The demand for fish as source of protein is increasing on daily basis due to increase in human population⁴. As an important part of the global food system, fish has a significant potential to contribute to the goal of reducing food and nutrition insecurity in the world. Fisheries has also made a significant contribution to the process of improving food security through the opportunities the sector provides for employment and income to millions of people⁵, either directly or indirectly. Despite the high biological value of fish, various diseases including parasitic infections pose a threat to its existence, hence, contributing to high fish mortalities and economic losses that threaten the abundance and diversity of indigenous of fish species⁶. Parasites play essential roles in natural biomes. They can control host population abundance, impact the range and proportion of communities and stabilize food webs^{7, 8, 9, 10}. Protozoa as fish parasites are relatively difficult to study when compared to other larger parasites, however, ecto- and endo-parasitic forms are very relevant in the spread of diseases in fish population. These parasites majorly attack the fish's gill epithelium and cause destruction of the skin and eventual dead of the fish since the fish may not be able to feed properly¹¹. Interaction between hosts and parasites is a complex relationship that can favour one or the other depending on a number of factors among which are parasite establishment, host defense mechanisms, susceptibility or resistance which define if the infections become established or not¹². Parasites are widely distributed in fish family in various geographic regions and they may serve as carriers of many larval parasitic forms that matures and cause serious diseases in many vertebrates including man¹³. The main source of parasitic infection in humans occur when fishes are improperly cooked/processed and are consumed raw¹⁴. Study on fish parasites is of utmost important since parasites have been shown to lower fish productivity, decrease fish health, making them more susceptible to other diseases and even cause mortalities in fish. Parasitic diseases have also been reported to cause significant damage in fish industry¹⁵ which directly impact negatively on the food safety and security. Although, various researchers have revealed rich parasitic fauna in freshwater fishes^{16, 17}, some of which are parasitic in the external surface of fish; others are parasitic in the internal organs. However, extensive investigation of parasites of Tilapias in Ureje River was lacking, hence an extensive investigation was carried out to determine the diversity of parasites of *O. niloticus* in Ureje River in Ado Ekiti, Ekiti State, South Western Nigeria.

Materials and methods

a) Study Area

Sixty samples of *O. niloticus* were purchased from a fish farm around Ureje River, a freshwater which lies between latitude 07°36'23.82"N and longitude 005°18'25.87"E in Ado local government area of Ekiti state, over a period of six (6) months (July – December, 2020). Their weights, standard lengths and total lengths were recorded for morphometric study. The fish were immediately subjected to parasitological examinations. Water from the river was added to the life specimen and then transported to the Microbiology laboratory of

the Department of Sciences and Laboratory Technology, Federal Polytechnic, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State in aerated plastic buckets.

b). Parasitological examination

Standard parasitological technique was employed for examination of sampled fish for parasitic organisms¹⁸. The skin, gills and fins were examined for ectoparasite using hand lens. The samples were eviscerated using scalpel blade. The tissues were placed on a Petri dish and 3ml of 0.9% saline solution were added and stirred using a mounted pin. Some drops of mixed solution were collected using dropper, placed on a microscope slide, covered with a cover slip and observed under a light microscope. External examination using hand lens for large crustaceans and lesions on skin and fin was employed and the observations noted. After examination of the external part, the organs were dissected to search out the internal parasites. Each fish sample was cut opened and the alimentary canal, liver, kidney and swim bladder, were examined for endo-parasites. The gills were removed carefully and kept in sterile round glass beaker containing saline solution. Few drops of this solution were placed on microscope slides, covered with cover slip and viewed under x40 magnification. The gastrointestinal tract was cut open, washed in Petri dish with 0.1% NaCl (Sodium Chloride) solution and further rinsed with 0.1% NaHCO₃ (Sodium Bicarbonate). This was then stained with Giemsa stain for 15 minutes and viewed at x40 and x100 magnification.

c). Identification of parasites

The emergence of any parasite was easily noticed by its wriggling movement in the saline solution under the microscope. The parasites were identified by comparing with the pictorial guide on fish parasites¹⁹. Identification of specimens to species level were undertaken and confirmed^{20, 21}. The prevalence, mean intensity and abundance data were calculated according to Bush²².

d). Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed by ANOVA two factors without replications according to Sokal and Rohlf²³ to compare seasonal variation in the three sites for each parameter. A significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Results

A total sixty *O. niloticus* samples were examined for the presence of parasites, 55% of the total population were infected with parasites (Table 1).

Table 1: Percentage of infection of *O. niloticus* in Ureje River

Variables	No. examined	No of infected	Infection rate (%)
<i>O. niloticus</i>	60	33	55

Infection was high in dry season than the rainy season in the fish species, but no seasonal variation in prevalence was observed between the two seasons (Table 2). Prevalence rate of parasites in *O. niloticus* was higher during the dry season (80%) than the rainy season (48%)

Table 2: Seasonal occurrence of parasites in *O. niloticus*

Season	No. examined	No. infected	Prevalence (%)
Rainy	50	24	48
Dry	10	8	80

The results in Fig 1 and 2 showed that there were variabilities in the height and weight of *O. niloticus* for the period of this experiment. The lower the height, the lower weight i.e increase or decrease in the length of the fish has similar trend in the corresponding weight of the same fish. This was observed throughout the experimental period (July to December). The height and weight of *O. niloticus* were subjected to regression analysis, which revealed a significant relationship between height and weight as r value (0.942, $H_0 P=0$; $H_1 P\neq 0$) is close to 1 (Fig 3). There is no difference in the height and weight hence we do not reject the null hypothesis.

The prevalence of parasites on *O. niloticus* from July to December ranged from 10 to 100 %, with mean prevalence of 45 %, mean intensity at 177 and mean abundance at 55 (Table 3)

Figure 1: Length/height (cm) of the *O. niloticus* from July to December

Figure 2: Weight (kg) of the *O. niloticus* from July to December

Figure 3: Relationship between height and weight ($y=12.81+44.43x$), $r=0.942$ ($H_0 P=0$; $H_1 P\neq 0$). There is significant relationship between height and weight as r value is close to 1.

Table 3 Prevalence of parasites and their distributions in *O. niloticus* from July to December

Month	IF/EF	N	P %	MI	MA
July	06/10	8	80.00	133	80
August	10/10	8	100.00	80	80
September	03/10	3	30.00	100	30
October	01/10	3	10.00	300	30
November	02/10	5	20.00	250	50
December	03/10	6	30.00	200	60
Mean	7/10	5.5	45	177	55

IF infected fish, EF examined fish, P prevalence, MI mean intensity, MA mean abundance

During this study, nine genera of Protozoa, three species of Nematode and one species of Trematode were isolated from different organs of *O. niloticus* (Table 4). The parasites infected the Slime, gills and intestines. *Tetrahymena* sp, *Ambiphyra* sp, *Chilodonella* sp and *Coccidia* sp were found in the slime, *Microsporidia* sp and *Myxozoa* sp were found in the intestine, *Trichodina* sp and *Piscinoodinium* sp were seen in both the slime and the gills while *Ichthyophthirius* sp was found in the gill. *Allocreadium* sp was the only Trematode isolated from the gill while *Capillaria* sp, *Contracaecum* sp and *Camallanus* sp were Nematodes isolated from the intestine. The prevalence of protozoa isolated from *O. niloticus* varied from 1.67% (*Chilodonella* and *Coccidia* sp) to an optimal prevalence value of 16.7% in *Piscinoodinium* sp. while *Allocreadium lobatum* has a prevalence value of 8.3%.

Table 4: Prevalence of parasites and their distributions in organs of *O. niloticus*

Taxonomic group	Genus	OE	EF	IF	N	P (%)	MI	MA
Protozoa	<i>Tetrahymena</i> sp	Slime	60	2	2	3.33	100	3.33
	<i>Ambiphrya</i> sp		60	2	2	3.33	100	3.33
	<i>Chilodonella</i> sp		60	1	1	1.67	100	1.67
	<i>Coccidia</i> sp		60	1	1	1.67	100	1.67
	<i>Microsporidia</i> sp	Intestine	60	1	1	1.67	100	1.67
	<i>Myxozoa</i> sp		60	1	1	1.67	100	1.67
	<i>Trichodina</i> sp	Slime & Gill	60	3	3	3.33	100	3.33
	<i>Piscinoodinium</i> sp		60	10	10	16.67	100	16.67
	<i>Ichthyophthirius</i> sp	Gill	60	2	2	3.33	100	3.33
Trematode	<i>Allocreadium lobatum</i>	Gill	60	5	5	8.33	100	8.33
Nematodes	<i>Capillaria</i> sp	Intestine	60	4	4	6.67	100	6.67
	<i>Contracaecum</i> sp		60	1	1	1.67	100	1.67
	<i>Camallanus</i> sp		60	1	1	1.67	100	1.67
Mean			60	2.62	2.62	4.23	100	4.23

OE organs examined, IF infected fish, EF examined fish, P prevalence, MI mean intensity, MA mean abundance

Discussion

This research was focused on the ectoparasites and endoparasites of *O. niloticus*. This research revealed that diverse parasites (protozoa, trematode and nematode) affected the slime, gill and intestine of the fish under study. These parasites were present in the slime and the intestine more than the gill of the fish samples in the river under study. The result from this study agrees with the work of Akoll et al.,²⁴ who observed that *O. niloticus* were highly susceptible to parasitic infections mainly by protozoan and monogenean. Protozoans are

opportunistic species common in juvenile of a wide range of fish species from most families. *Trichodina* parasite often attacks freshwater fish²⁵ and are found extensively on the body surface of fish due to the presence of mucous on the body surface that serve as food for *Trichodina* parasite. Also, constant interaction between the environment and body surface of fish predisposes fish to direct attack by *Trichodina* spp.²⁶. The presence of these parasites on gills and skin of the fish may not affect the fish health, however, an increase in number may lead to severe infection and eventually death of fish²⁷. Feeding by *Trichodina* spp. on the epithelial layer of the gill surface and fish skin will cause hyperplasia (proliferation) of the epithelial cells, gill destruction, and filamentous merging. The ability of gills to retain ultimate respiratory, excretory roles and the skin to perform ideal osmoregulatory activities will be affected by ectoparasite infestation. The sign of ectoparasites infestation could be, and/or lead to ulcerative skin lesions, which allow for secondary infection from bacteria and fungi²⁸. The lesions formed due to the presence of these parasites may initiate a hyperplastic and edematous process in the fish gills triggering alterations in the gas and ion exchange surface with consequences for the fish metabolism²⁹. Furthermore, *Trichodina* spp. could be an indicator for the presence of nitrite, nitrates and ammonia which increase the number of protozoal infestations in polluted water. Parasitic infestations found in fish from Ureje river were probably due to the poor water quality of the river, which may be associated with the drainage systems of Ado-Ekiti that aid high rain influx during the rainy season. Poor water quality has been identified as one of the factors responsible for parasite infestation of fishes. Water quality plays a crucial role in disrupting the balance between the host and the pathogen³⁰. Infection may be influenced by poor water quality and high content of organic matter^{31, 32, 33, 34}. The level of organic matter in the water and adverse environmental temperature were significant contributing factors (induce quick succession) for parasitic disease outbreaks³⁰. When fish are exposed to adverse stress situation, the disease occurs³⁵. Acidic waters and inadequate dissolved oxygen as well as increased stress level make fish vulnerable to diseases and parasitic outbreaks that could lead to eventual death. *Ichthyophthirius multifiliis* is a ubiquitous, holotrichous parasitic ciliate that affects all freshwater fishes. It is one of the biggest responsible for significant economic losses in fish farms worldwide³⁶. It's found as a small white spots on the skin, fins and the gills. The parasite may interfere with osmoregulation due to the disruption of the contiguous epithelium. Fish infestation is favoured by low temperatures^{29, 37} and the influence of temperature determines the rate of infestations especially in cold regions²⁸. The maximum length observed in this study was 20.3 cm weighing 0.152kg. Bwanika et al.,³⁹ reported an average length of 20cm in *O. niloticus* however, previous study has shown that Tilapia fish could attain a maximum length of 62 cm and 3.65kg in weight⁴⁰. We observed that parasitic infection increased as the length and weight increased, this observation is similar to the work of Robert,⁴¹ who showed that parasite increases with the fish length and Golder et al.,⁴² suggested that the increase in parasitization could be due to yearly parasitic larva accumulation as the fish grow older. Also, Emere⁴³ reported that food/diet could contribute to parasites burden. The high infection observed in bigger fish in this study could be attributed to the larger surface area in bigger fish that gives room for multiplication of infection compared to lesser surface area in smaller fish. Furthermore, changes in diet as

smaller fishes grows could give room for multiplication of infection⁴⁴. The three genera of nematodes isolated in this study were found in the intestine. Nematodes such as *Contracaecum* are common in a wide variety of fish of diverse families. Okaka and Omoigberale⁴⁵ reported that nematode parasites infecting fish population were found in the intestine. *Contracaecum* sp. was isolated from the gastrointestinal tract of tilapia fish with a low prevalence level of 1.7% which is lower when compared with the work of Gichohi⁴⁶ who reported 33.8% prevalence rate of *Contracaecum* sp. in Tilapia. This difference in prevalence can be ascribed to environmental factors, type of nutrition and water quality.

Conclusion

This is the first report of parasitic infection of *O. niloticus* in Ureje River. A total of 13 genera of both ecto- and endo-parasites were found in *O. niloticus* in Ureje River. This study has shown that tilapia from the study site were infested with parasites including Protozoans, Nematodes and trematodes. The presence of these parasites could constitute a serious problem for fish production in the area. Infection could be influenced by high rain influx during the rainy season and low rain influx during the dry season as fishes are susceptible to heavy infestation with parasites during the early rain. However, differences in the abundance and prevalence of these parasites may be due to host-pathogen relationship depending on whether or not the immune system compromised. Fish parasitism constitutes a major threat to fish productivity, and the increased demand on fish as a ready and safe source of protein to humans should trigger further studies on fish fauna and their parasites, and their identification to species level using molecular techniques. Also, factors influencing the abundance of parasites in this river should also be taken into account during such study.

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